

Traceability of Meat and Meat Products

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Abstract

Traceability is a system of maintaining integrity of animal or their products identification across the food supply chain. A robust traceability system helps in mitigating and management of disease outbreaks or food crisis by identifying the origin of the product and thereby implementing control programs. Traceability lends a hand in ensuring food safety and quality assurance. Meat traceability has two components, one is the traceability of live animal and another is the traceability of meat in its processing plant until it reaches its consumer. Live animal traceability at the farm is done using ear tags, Radio Frequency Identifying Tags, transponder etc. till it reaches abattoirs and meat processing plants wherein, traceability in carry out using radiofrequency chips or barcodes and it go on by adding additional information at each stage of the food supply chain till it reach consumer's hand. Molecular meat traceability is the most reliable method in meat traceability. Most of the developed countries have adopted meat traceability to aid in obtaining access to the international meat markets. Recently, India, holding high the first position in exporting buffalo meat, has also developed a buffalo breed traceability system.

Introduction

Now a day, consumers are much concerns about the quality of the food they are having, freshness of the food, how the foods were produced, processed as well as distributed. Due to the raising cases of meat borne diseases, meat authentication of animal species and religious sentiment, traceability and safety of the meat or meat products, has become the centerpiece to the consumers

as well as for the meat industry. Codex Alimentarius Commission (CAC) defined traceability as: “*The ability to follow the movement of a food through specified stage(s) of production, processing and distribution*” (CAC, 2006). Traceability is a system of maintaining credibility of identification of animals or their products across the food supply chain i.e. farm-to-retailer (McKean 2001).

Traceability can be used as a potential risk management tool in the food supply chain to detain the supply of unsafe food by withdrawing or recall of food products by the manufactures. A vigorous traceability system helps in reducing the response time when there is any animal disease outbreak. It can identify the causative agent, ingredient or source, country of origin as well as location of the implicated product with rapid and reliable information.

Livestock traceability is the ability to follow an animal or group of animals during all stages of its life (OIE, 2018). Since the spread of animal diseases like Bovine Spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) and Avian Influenza (Bird flu), traceability has emerged as a major paradigm for meat quality assurance. Traceability guarantees the meat producers, packers, processors, wholesalers, exporters, retailers, and consumers by assuring that the livestock and meat are identified through all or parts of life cycle, and that the information are authentic (Smith *et al.*, 2008). Thus, traceability ensure meat quality assurance by facilitating farm-to fork tracing and tracking and enabling food recalling, controlling disease outbreak, protecting public health, and encouraging hygienic production practices.

To obtain a place in the international meat market, countries must adopt livestock and meat traceability which gives authentic information on animal identification by providing unique numbers, registration system, identifying the premises involved in the raising of the meat animals and their harvesting. Traceability system also includes a vigorous database for uploading, updating and retrieving information, with sufficient equipment and personnel to implement and constantly ensure that the above tasks are done in solemn. Techniques for verifying traceability are also an important requirement of the meat traceability system. Molecular techniques like microsatellite genotyping and single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) can be used to confirm the origin of animal. Developed countries which have adopted livestock traceability are Brazil, the United States, Australia, New Zealand, Argentina, Canada, Uruguay, the European Union, Japan, South Korea, and Mexico (Ted and Glynn, 2012). Hence meat produced under completely traceable environments can easily find market access in different countries, thereby boosting the export prospects of the commodity.

Farm-to-fork traceability of meat or products starts with monitoring the live animal or livestock in the farm, slaughtering animal in abattoirs, processing of meat in meat plants and other food premises, distribution to wholesalers and retailers and to the moment the product is placed on the consumer's table.

Live Animal Traceability

Live animal traceability is an important part of meat and meat products traceability system. Animals are identified using laser-printed visible ear tags, radio frequency identification devices (RFIDs), quick response (QR) code, and bar-coded ear tags. It helps in ownership determination, livestock insurance, scientific feeding and management (*viz.*, history of vaccine, treatments), performance recording and breeding. Registration of farms and abattoirs helps in tracking of the farm-of-origin if any disease is detected during meat inspection or any disease outbreaks from consumption of meat products; and thus helps in implementation of effective disease control programs in that specific farm or abattoir. Traceability of farm-to-fork helps in acquiring meat quality assurance by supplying safe meat free from physical, chemical, and biological hazards as well as documentation of food safety hazards.

Methods of Live Animal Identification

Different methods of traceability have been used in animal as well as meat and meat products traceability are described below.

- ***Visual Tagging***

Animal's number is printed on a plastic tag, number is readable.

- ***Bar-coded Tags***

Bar code is an optical machine-readable representation of data. Originally, barcodes represented data in the widths (lines) and the spacing of parallel lines and may be referred to as linear or 1D (1 dimensional) barcodes. Data like name of the owner or farm, date of birth of the animal, body weight, vaccination and treatment, etc. are stored in it. Every country has its own code for identification and the data is stored between these lines. Since it is a one-dimensional system, it stores less data as compared to the quick response data matrix which is a 2-dimensional data capture mechanism. (Rao *et al.*, 2022).

- ***Radio Frequency Identification Devices***

In recent years, RFID technology has become popular for the identification of items in the management of global supply chain. Radio waves are employed by RFID technology to identify

objects automatically. This is accomplished by identifying and storing a serial number with other relevant information, on a microchip that is attached to an antenna. This bundle is called an RFID tag. The antenna enables the chip to transmit the identification information to a reader. The reader converts the radio waves reflected back from the RFID tag into digital information that can be passed on to an enterprise information system RFID can empower a broad spectrum of application and can be used in up- stream warehouse and distribution management down to retail outlet operations (Rao *et al.*, 2022).

- ***Quick Response Code-Based Tags***

The quick response (QR) code is one of the traceability systems that have been introduced to the food industries as a two-dimensional barcode. The QR code can be embedded with text, video, advertisements, personal information etc. The QR code can be integrated into users' smart phone applications, where it can scan and decode information and messages about products that the QR code provides.

Traceability at Abattoirs and Meat Processing Plant

Slaughter house or processing plant traceability is generally adopted in large slaughter houses or processing plants meant for export purposes and were adopted by most of the developed countries. At the time of slaughtering the animals in the abattoirs proper records keeping coded in their tags are maintained. At the processing plants, RFID chip could be applied either at gambrel (hook for suspending carcass) or at bin (container for holding meat cuts) in the fabrication floor. In gambrel identification, after the carcass is hung into the hooks or gambrel, the information coded in the animal tags along with date of slaughter, lot number and post-slaughter weight are added into RFID chip embedded in gambrel and general information system. Gambrel RFID system will works up to the point of fabrication of primal parts as the carcass is remove from the hook at this point for the purpose of fabrication. At this step, RFID chips are attached to the bins for carrying the primal cuts and all information gathered up to that point is transfer to the chip in the bin.

Another method of using RFID chip is the board identification, where chip is attached to the cutting board to avoid recall of the entire lot of meat due to any contamination from the cutting board. Board chip enables individual tracking and individual recall in case of any contamination and also boards could be sterilized between different primal cuts. Finally, the cuts and scrap of individual animal are moved to individual cutters for later separation and packaging.

Information in bins and boards are transferred to general information system and this information should correlates with the position of packaging conveyor to establish traceability at the individual animal level. Lastly, the product is packaged with a bar code or RFID label assigned to it. This is the starting point for the traceability in next segment in the meat chain (Mennecke and Townsend, 2005).

At retailer and distributors level, machine readable codes are scanned to obtain the whole information right from the production up to distribution. Consumers are the last part of the supply chain; they can gain the information from the numerical codes and public access website (Yordanov and Angelova, 2006).

Molecular Traceability of Meat and Meat Products

Contrasting geographical traceability, genetic traceability identifies individual, breed or species (animal or its products) using DNA sequences. Identification of animals with a tamper-proof system is a core requirement for any livestock traceability system. Apart from using geographical traceability like visual tags, ear tags, RFID, and QR codes in livestock identification, molecular based traceability also exists. Molecular traceability is based on the variability within the DNA of individuals and is used as a tool for the verification of traceability and is the most reliable. It enables traceability verification by comparing labeled meat samples with the reference sample preserved during the slaughter process. The prerequisite for the molecular meat traceability is preservation of reference samples of each animal or batch (blood, tissue, or hair follicle samples) collected from the animal prior to or during the slaughter of the animal and preserved of the product until the period of its consumption by the consumers. Identifying and confirming the source of meat to a particular individual when it is packed individually or as a batch is the challenge to be resolved by molecular meat traceability techniques. DNA tracking can link meat back to the farm of origin, bypassing the expensive step of tracking through the plant.

Microsatellite genotyping and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism genotyping are the commonly used methods for molecular meat traceability. Microsatellite markers are short, repeated units of DNA usually less than 100 base pairs that occur in multiple places in the genome. Microsatellite markers can be used for both individual traceability and breed traceability. Individual traceability is obtained by comparing the genotypic pattern of the test sample and reference sample collected during slaughter, while for breed traceability the genotypic pattern of the test sample has to be compared with the already available data on genotypic pattern of different

breeds. For the purpose of genotyping, genomic DNA of both the meat sample and reference sample has to be extracted using the standard protocols. A method for breed identification of buffalo meat using eight sets of microsatellite markers was developed (Bheemashankar *et al.*, 2017). SNPs are single base changes in DNA sequences. SNPs represent the simplest type of genetic marker. After identifying the gene of test sample, it can be screen for the presence of SNPs. Broad database on SNPs of livestock and mammalian species are already available (Choi *et al.*, 2016). A SNP-based molecular traceability system has been developed for detection of beef products protected with four European Geographic Indication (Negrini *et al.*, 2008).

Meat Traceability in India

India stands first in exporting cara-beef in the world (APEDA, 2016) and owing to the emergence of certain breed names as brand names, draws the attention of researchers for developing techniques for certification of meat products with its breed of origin. Developing a traceability system for Indian buffalo breeds is extremely pertinent due to its export potential. Keeping it in view, Indian Council of Agricultural Research- National Research Centre on Meat (ICAR-NRCM), Hyderabad has developed a complete buffalo meat traceability system in 2020. Buffalo meat traceability system using sixteen digit RFID ear tags, RFID reader and bar code has been developed to effectively trace back the source of meat. Besides, identifying the origin of buffalo breed, providing food safety and authenticity; buffalo breed traceability also help in developing meat breeds suitable for the diverse agro-climatic conditions.

For the purpose of exporting quality meat products, Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development (APEDA) has developed an online traceability system where it offers registration service to meat processing establishments to apply for health certificate having compulsory microbiological and other tests done by Government laboratory.

Conclusion

Traceability has become a critical component of agro-food industry for mitigating the risk related to freshness of food, food-borne diseases, and religious sentiment in order to provide quality assurance and food safety to the consumers. Farm-to-fork traceability system in meat and mat products commence with the identification of the individual live animal at the farm level through its processing plant, distributors and retailers up to the consumer's table. Traceability makes the whole supply chain process transparent by monitoring its quality throughout its movement. Among the methods used for identification of animal or meat or product, molecular

traceability method is the most reliable. Though most of the developed countries have adopted traceability up to the fullness in meat supply chain, for developing country like India meat traceability is a novel technique and has started with a recent breed traceability technology of buffalo meat. Traceability of meat also helps in accessing international meat market. It is recommended that public and private companies should grasp the opportunities to make their consumers feel safe of the food or product they are having by adopting traceability as well as to have their market opportunities.

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